

Research Article

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Comparative Analysis of Sustainability Communication Strategies of Thai and Global Brand Restaurants on Social Media and Websites

Kanokkan Bunchabusabong^{1,*} , Jukkrit Tiwasuppachai² , Shawanluck Kunathikornkit³

¹School of Communication Arts, University of The Thai Chamber of Commerce, Thailand

²Institute of Harbour.Space@UTCC, University of The Thai Chamber of Commerce, Thailand

³Faculty of Business Administration for Society, Srinakharinwirot University, Thailand

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Correspondence:
kanokkan.b@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In recent years, sustainability has become a crucial concern in the food industry, with restaurants playing a significant role in promoting sustainable practices. Consumers increasingly demand transparency and responsibility, pushing restaurants to adopt and effectively communicate their sustainability efforts. This research investigates the sustainability communication strategies of Thai and global brand restaurants on social media and official websites. The purpose of this study is to compare how Thai and global brand restaurants communicate their sustainability practices. The study used a content analysis approach to analyze posts from Facebook, Instagram, and the websites of the Thai restaurant brand “S&P Syndicate” and the global restaurant brand “Minor Food.” The measures used to evaluate sustainability communication are qualitative. The study identifies and analyzes recurring themes related to sustainability. Additionally, it assesses the tone of the messages to categorize the tone of communication, examining how these elements support and enhance the communication of sustainability initiatives. The coding sheet was designed based on four theories: the Triple Bottom Line (People, Planet, and Profit), Integrated Marketing Communication, the Elaboration Likelihood Model, and Narrative. The findings reveal that the content themes of S&P Syndicate emphasize environmental sustainability through eco-friendly product designs, recycling programs, conservation projects, and community inclusion. Minor Food, on the other hand, focuses more on people development by integrating comprehensive health programs, educational partnerships, training programs, and community empowerment initiatives. Minor Food adopts more innovative technologies and has a broader global communication and impact than S&P Syndicate’s local focus. The message tone of S&P Syndicate presents community engagement activities in a formal and traditional public relations style, while Minor Food encourages a wider range of stakeholders and aligns with the global agenda in a professional image, demonstrating a passion for sustainable achievement. This study provides insights into how Thai and global brand’s unique focus and methodologies contribute to their overall sustainability goals, offering valuable perspectives for businesses aiming to enhance their sustainability communication strategies.

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As the global landscape becomes increasingly attuned to environmental and social challenges, consumers are demonstrating a heightened consciousness toward responsible consumption. Responsible consumer behavior becomes increasingly pertinent, serving as a cornerstone for advancing comprehension of sustainable consumption (Hinton & Goodman, 2010). This behavior offers a foundation for businesses and policymakers to develop strategies that align with the growing demand for environmentally and socially responsible products. It contributes to sustainable development, underscoring the pivotal role of consumers in driving positive environmental and social change through their everyday purchasing decisions (Young et al., 2010).

Brand sustainability, evolving from responsible corporate practices to a contemporary focus on environmental and social considerations, encapsulates a transformative journey. Originating in corporate social responsibility, it expanded to encompass financial facets, emphasizing the firm's maintenance and shareholder benefit (Montiel, 2008). A pivotal shift towards environmental concerns ushered in the era of 'green' initiatives, underscoring the finite nature of earth's resources. Acknowledging brands' intrinsic 'sustainable' quality, the crux lies in their judicious management, recognizing their vulnerability to decline without due attention (Schultz & Block, 2015). Brand sustainability transcends a mere buzzword, emerging as an indispensable element for ensuring enduring success and positive impact, navigating the intricate interplay of consumer expectations and global challenges (Hargreaves et al., 2012).

Various studies have highlighted the significance of brand sustainability in the hospitality industry. For instance, Hussain et al. (2020) explored how sustainable brand equity and marketing innovation influence market performance, considering the mediating role of sustainable competitive advantage. Sowamber et al. (2017) examined how sustainability practices affect the behaviors and attitudes of consumers in the hospitality sector. Similarly, Bartels and Hoogendam (2011) investigated the influence of social identity and attitudes towards sustainability brands on consumer purchasing decisions for organic products.

Jang et al. (2015) investigate the connection between environmentally friendly practices, consumer attachment, and loyalty, highlighting the moderating role of green consciousness. The findings indicate that green practices significantly influence consumers' emotional attachment to a store. This attachment, in turn, positively affects both store loyalty and product loyalty. Moreover, consumers with a high level of green consciousness demonstrated stronger attachments to green stores and exhibited greater loyalty.

Evidence suggests that sustainable brand equity positively affects market performance in the hospitality industry, including restaurants, by attracting customers and emphasizing sustainability efforts (Hussain et al., 2020). This is crucial in promoting sustainable practices as consumers increasingly demand transparency and accountability, prompting restaurants to adopt and communicate their sustainability initiatives more effectively (Higgins-Desbiolles & Wijesinghe, 2021).

Building on this, effective communication of sustainability efforts is vital for restaurants to meet these consumer expectations, enhance brand reputation, foster consumer trust, and influence purchasing decisions. Strong communication strategies can reinforce a brand's credibility and

impact consumer choices, particularly as transparency in environmental practices becomes more important (Shafieizadeh & Tao, 2020).

While numerous studies focus on the importance of brand sustainability in the restaurant industry, limited attention has been given to examining how brands communicate their sustainability efforts. There is a noticeable gap in the research specifically addressing how restaurant brands use social media and websites to convey their sustainability initiatives and increase awareness and customer engagement.

Bridging this gap would provide valuable insights for developing sustainable brand communication strategies in the restaurant industry that effectively resonate with consumers. It would also help restaurants better understand how to utilize digital platforms, such as social media and websites, to enhance customer engagement, build trust, and promote their sustainability efforts in a more transparent and compelling manner.

This study, titled “Comparative Analysis of Sustainability Communication Strategies of Thai and Global Brand Restaurants on Social Media and Websites,” aims to investigate and compare the sustainability communication strategies employed by Thai and global restaurant brands on social media platforms and official websites.

The research question guiding this study is: What are the different approaches to sustainability communication strategies between Thai and global restaurant brands? The specific objectives of this study are: 1) To examine how Thai brand restaurants communicate their sustainability practices. 2) To investigate how global brand restaurants communicate their sustainability practices. 3) To compare the sustainability communication strategies of Thai and global restaurant brands.

This study explores the sustainability communication strategies employed by Thai and global restaurant brands, specifically on social media platforms and official websites. It examines how these brands communicate their sustainability efforts, the types of messages and narratives they use, and the effectiveness of these communications in engaging consumers. To achieve these objectives, the study adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining content analysis of social media posts and website content with surveys or interviews to gather insights from both brand managers and consumers. This approach aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of current practices and to identify best practices for sustainability communication within the restaurant industry.

The research focuses on the sustainability communication strategies of the Thai restaurant brand “S&P Syndicate” and the global restaurant brand “Minor Food” on social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram, as well as their official websites. It employs a content analysis approach to evaluate the sustainability messages conveyed by these brands, analyzing posts from their social media accounts and websites to identify recurring themes and assess the tone of the messages. The coding sheet for this analysis is based on four theoretical frameworks: the Triple Bottom Line (People, Planet, and Profit), Integrated Marketing Communication, the Elaboration Likelihood Model, and Narrative Theory.

The findings of this study are expected to provide valuable insights into the different approaches taken by Thai and global brands in their sustainability communications. By comparing the strategies of S&P Syndicate and Minor Food, the research will highlight the unique focuses and methodologies that contribute to their overall sustainability goals. These insights can offer practical

guidance for other businesses seeking to enhance their sustainability communication strategies and engage more effectively with their audiences on environmental and social issues.

Literature Review

The study uses a theoretical framework for designing the coding sheet based on five theories:

1. The Triple Bottom Line: People, Planet, and Profit
2. Integrated Marketing Communication
3. The Elaboration Likelihood Model
4. Narrative
5. Sustainable Development Goals
6. Sustainable Brand

The Triple Bottom Line

The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) framework measures business performance and organizational success across three dimensions: economic, social, and environmental (Goel, 2010). It is crucial for sustainable development, as it emphasizes the interconnectedness of economic, environmental, and social value (Hammer & Pivo, 2017). TBL focuses on three core areas: people, planet, and profit. It represents a concerted effort to integrate economic, environmental, and social considerations into a company's evaluation and decision-making processes. This approach establishes guiding principles for companies to assess the overall impact of their actions, both positive and negative (Arowoshegbe et al., 2016). TBL is regarded as a paradigm of sustainable business practice (Glac, 2015).

Nevertheless, the study of the traditional TBL framework is inadequate for encompassing the full scope of sustainability, particularly in engineering and social aspects, and shifting focus from broad sustainability discussions to micro-level assessments (Tseng et al., 2020).

Integrated Marketing Communication

Many businesses use social media to engage with interested parties to shape their sustainability strategies. Brand sustainability is directly linked to the level of online engagement with the community and stakeholders on CSR topics (Al Adwan & Altrjman, 2024). Digital marketing using various communication tools can contribute to sustainable development, from data access and awareness creation to communication that influences behavior toward sustainability and purchasing decisions (Rosário et al., 2023). Effective marketing management can establish a strong foundation for brand sustainability, serving as a key driver in integrating sustainability issues from both strategic and practical perspectives (Aripin, 2023).

Corporate Brand

The corporate brand is a valuable strategic resource that reflects the organization's identity and values (Balmer, 2023). It enhances brand alliances by providing unique information to consumers (Mohan, 2018). For consideration in the business aspect, The corporate brand can assume a more prominent role within the brand portfolio, and its use as a master brand helps maximize the portfolio's overall goals (Aaker, 2004). The corporate brand is a key resource for achieving a

sustainable competitive advantage which its dominance in fulfilling the essential characteristics required to maintain long-term competitiveness (Veselinova, 2016).

Consistency of Sustainability Message

Brand management should ensure that Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) efforts and the foundation work in harmony, aligning the foundation's goals with the company's vision. It should also maintain consistency in the visual attributes of the foundation and the company while ensuring that the foundation's activities effectively reinforce the brand (Monfort & Villagra, 2016). A well-designed brand image based on sustainable development principles can significantly enhance a brand's market presence and foster consumer loyalty by addressing both practical and aspirational needs of the audience (Li-rui, 2015).

Integrating of Channels & Coordination of Communication Tools

Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) activities enhance an organization's competitiveness and efficiency by focusing on results. This approach requires the use of diverse, practical, and continually evolving marketing communication methods, effectively implemented across various communication channels to reach the target audience with greater precision (Bormane & Putans, 2022).

For Message Tone Analysis, the Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) framework is applied. This framework examines how the restaurants integrate various communication channels (website, Facebook, Instagram) to deliver a cohesive sustainability message. The analysis looks for consistency in themes, tone, and visual elements across platforms, assessing the effectiveness of their integrated communication strategies.

The Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM)

This theory provides a general framework for organizing, classifying, and understanding the fundamental processes that drive the effectiveness of persuasive communication, depending on the communicator's level of interest in the topic being discussed. The main idea assumes that individuals process persuasive messages in various ways which focuses on fostering attitude change (Karoline et al., 2023). Marketers can enhance viral advertising by using emotional and peripheral cues to capture attention and encourage sharing, which boosts brand visibility and engagement. Tailoring strategies to the product and audience ensures maximum campaign impact (Segev & Fernandes, 2023).

The ELM is utilized to analyze the sustainability messages to determine whether they follow the *central route* (detailed, logical arguments), which involves persuasion through the detailed content of the message, leading to attitude changes that result from conscious and thoughtful decision-making. This process requires strong motivation to engage with the message and the ability to critically evaluate its content (Karoline et al., 2023) and persuasion involves a focus on the strength of message arguments (Wagner & Petty, 2022).

Peripheral route (emotional appeals, endorsements) refers to whether the message is accepted or rejected without much regard to the necessary or expected attitude change. Identifying the type of persuasion used helps to understand the intent and impact of the messages on the audience,

providing insights into how these messages influence public perception (Karoline et al., 2023) or persuaded by one of several low-effort mechanisms (Wagner & Petty, 2022).

Narrative Theory

Page (2018) elaborates on how narrative storytelling serves as a central form of communication on social media, allowing individuals and groups to share experiences, construct identities, and build communities; his study demonstrates how social media transforms traditional narrative practices, fostering new forms of self-expression, social connection, and public discourse in the digital age. These online narratives are inherently interactive and co-created, with multiple contributors shaping stories through comments, shares, and other forms of participation. Where diverse media forms—such as text, images, videos, and emojis—are used to enhance communication and engagement. By creating compelling narratives that engage and mobilize supporters across different regions, activists can amplify their impact in local cultural, political, and social contexts and foster global solidarity through transnational collaboration (Ciszek, 2017). Lastly, Narrative Theory is used for visual and textual analysis. This framework examines how visuals (images, videos) and textual content are used to convey sustainability messages. Narrative theory helps to understand the storytelling techniques and their effectiveness in engaging the audience and promoting sustainability initiatives.

Sustainable Development Goals

From TBL framework subsequently gained broad recognition within business and development sectors, profoundly shaping sustainability policy frameworks across a multitude of organizations. The TBL (Triple Bottom Line) framework serves as a foundational paradigm, offering both structural coherence and strategic direction for sustainable development initiatives. According to United Nation (2015) It provides the conceptual underpinnings of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), formally adopted by the United Nations (2015), with an overarching mandate to promote systematic, collaborative global action toward sustainable development by 2030. Recognizing that sustainable development is beyond the capacity of any single nation or sector to achieve independently, the SDGs emphasize the critical need for cross-national partnerships and cooperative networks. Such collaborations are essential to foster resource-sharing, technological exchange, knowledge dissemination, and financial support mechanisms that collectively target poverty alleviation, inequality reduction, and comprehensive environmental stewardship.

Sustainable Brand

In 1987, the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development introduced a widely adopted definition of sustainability, describing it as a society's capacity to meet present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own to 2030, The United Nations announced 17 Agenda of Sustainable Development Goals.

From the study “Implementation of the triple bottom line concept to improve sustainable marketing performance” Sustainable marketing, based on the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) framework, plays a significance role in promoting economic, social, and environmental sustainability by enhancing credibility and encouraging responsible practices. It has evolved from

focusing on production and consumer orientation to a broader societal perspective that prioritizes social goals. Integrating environmental values into marketing strategies is crucial for gaining a competitive advantage and driving sustainable development. Ultimately, the goal of sustainable marketing is to create a critical mass of informed consumers, leading to meaningful societal change through authentic marketing communications and strategic initiatives (Purnama, 2024).

Grubor and Milovanov (2017) elaborated that brand sustainability goes beyond mere environmental considerations, embracing a holistic approach integrating environmental, social, and economic dimensions. The evolving definition underscores the importance of brands aligning with broader sustainability goals, incorporating ethical practices, and demonstrating a commitment to societal and environmental well-being. In essence, brand sustainability in this context involves a strategic and integrated approach surpassing mere environmental responsibility, recognizing the interconnectedness of social, economic, and environmental factors in shaping a brand's identity and impact.

In summary, brand sustainability transcends a mere trend, emerging as a pivotal force shaping consumer behavior across generations. Originating from corporate social responsibility, it evolved into a commitment to long-term viability and societal well-being. The sustainability brand model emphasizes an integrated understanding, highlighting interconnected sustainability dimensions. This resonates in the strategic alignment of sustainability with consumer expectations, ensuring a brand's enduring success. Across generations and diverse retail platforms, brand sustainability significantly influences consumer choices. Recognizing its impact is crucial for businesses to tailor effective strategies, aligning with evolving preferences in the dynamic market landscape.

This study provides an overview of brand sustainability, followed by a discussion of the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) framework, which serves as a basis for evaluating organizational communication strategies related to the three dimensions: people, planet, and profit. This framework enables a clearer understanding of the organization's communication focus and the priority given to each aspect in conjunction with sustainability principles and SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) to ensure a more comprehensive analysis.

Method

Sample and Data Collection

The sampling of this paper is purposive sampling. The sample selection in this study was a Thai brand restaurant and a global brand restaurant that are well-known and outstanding in sustainability communication. S&P Syndicate, representing the Thai brand restaurant, and Minor Food, representing the global brand restaurant, were chosen for their exemplary sustainability practices and their recognized efforts in communicating these initiatives effectively.

S&P Syndicate and Minor Food, corporate brands that own various restaurant brands in Thailand and emphasize sustainability communication. S&P Syndicate Public Company Limited operates 18 brands, including S&P, Maison, Patara, and Umenohana, and has received several recognitions such as the SET ESG Rating 2023. Minor Food, part of the Minor International Group, oversees 32 brands, including The Pizza Company, Sizzler, Swensen's, and The Coffee Club, operating in 24 countries including Thailand, Canada, the UAE, Mexico, and Romania. The study examines content on these corporate websites and social media platforms, focusing on sustainability communication.

The primary sources for data collection in this study included official websites, Facebook, and Instagram. The official websites of the selected restaurants were reviewed, focusing on the sustainability sections, news updates, and other relevant content that provided insights into the companies' sustainability efforts. Facebook was analyzed for posts, images, and videos related to sustainability initiatives, allowing for an understanding of how these brands communicate with their audience on this platform. Similarly, Instagram was examined for images, videos, and captions that conveyed sustainability messages, offering a visual and textual perspective on their sustainability communication strategies. Content analysis was employed for the data collection method, using a coding sheet to systematically gather posts, images, videos, and textual content related to sustainability. The data collection spanned from July 1, 2023, to June 30, 2024.

Measures

The measures used to evaluate sustainability communication are qualitative in nature and include several key indicators. Firstly, Content themes are identified to recognize recurring themes related to sustainability, such as environmental initiatives, ethical sourcing, waste reduction, and community engagement. This helps to understand how these topics are prioritized and communicated by the brands. Secondly, Message Tone is assessed to categorize the tone of communication as informative, persuasive, or emotional, the use of visuals (images, videos), and textual content in conveying sustainability messages, examining how these elements support and enhance the communication of sustainability initiatives.

Data Analysis

The collected data will be analyzed using qualitative methods guided by four theoretical frameworks. The Triple Bottom Line (People, Planet, Profit) with SDGs framework is used to analyze content themes by identifying and categorizing content related to the three bottom lines: social (People), environmental (Planet), and economic (Profit) aspects. By linking these themes to relevant Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the study evaluates how restaurants align their sustainability communication with global standards.

For Message Tone Analysis, the Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) framework is applied. This framework examines how the restaurants integrate various communication channels (website, Facebook, Instagram) to deliver a cohesive sustainability message. The analysis looks for consistency in themes, tone, and visual elements across platforms, assessing the effectiveness of their integrated communication strategies. The Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) is utilized to analyze the sustainability messages to determine whether they follow the central route (detailed, logical arguments) or peripheral route (emotional appeals, endorsements). Identifying the type of persuasion used helps to understand the intent and impact of the messages on the audience, providing insights into how these messages influence public perception. Lastly, Narrative Theory is used for visual and textual analysis. Examines how visuals (images, videos) and textual content are used to convey sustainability messages. Narrative theory helps to understand the storytelling techniques and their effectiveness in engaging the audience and promoting sustainability initiatives.

The study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the sustainability communication strategies employed by S&P Syndicate and Minor Food. This approach ensures a thorough

understanding of how these brands communicate their sustainability efforts and the effectiveness of their strategies in influencing their audience.

Results

This section presents the conclusion of the content analysis in three parts. The first part presents the content analysis conclusion of sustainability communication strategies of Thai brand restaurants on social media and websites: "S&P Syndicate." The second part presents the content analysis conclusion of sustainability communication strategies of global brand restaurants on social media and websites: "Minor Food Group." The third part presents the comparative analysis of sustainability communication strategies of Thai and global brand restaurants on social media and websites. In each part, the studies show the key findings in two topics, including content themes analysis and message tone.

Sustainability Communication strategies of Thai brand restaurants on social media and websites: "S&P Syndicate"

This part studies how Thai brand restaurants communicate sustainability on social media and websites, focusing on "S&P Syndicate." The research results are presented in two parts as follows.

Content themes analysis

The Three Bottom Line (People, Planet, Profit). The findings show that S&P Syndicate has demonstrated unwavering dedication to sustainable development, prioritizing the three bottom lines: People, Planet, and Profit. This approach emphasizes social responsibility, environmental stewardship, and economic viability. By aligning their initiatives with key Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), S&P integrates these principles into their core operations. This section explores how S&P Syndicate effectively communicates its commitment to these values through various content and communication strategies, underscoring their role as a socially responsible corporation.

People

The findings show that S&P Syndicate particularly focuses on the "People" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory, emphasizing health and well-being, equality and inclusion, reducing inequality, and sustainable community development. The content analysis results are as follows. Health and Well-being: S&P Syndicate communicates a strong commitment to health and well-being, aligning with SDG 3, which aims to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all ages. Their content emphasizes comprehensive health insurance for employees, which provides a safety net and ensures access to essential health services. Community health initiatives are also a focal point, with significant projects designed to enhance the quality of life for local populations. For example, S&P organizes charity concerts and health campaigns, showcasing their proactive approach to community health. Additionally, the company's emphasis on food safety, through measures such as IPHA accreditation and participation in the "No Reuse Frying Oil" project, highlights their dedication to providing safe and healthy food options for customers. These

messages collectively underscore S&P's comprehensive approach to promoting well-being within the company and the broader community.

Equality and Inclusion: In promoting equality and inclusion, S&P Syndicate aligns with SDG 5, which focuses on achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls. The company's content highlights significant recognitions such as the "Outstanding Female Executive" award, which celebrates the achievements of female leaders within the organization. This recognition not only honors individual accomplishments but also promotes a culture of gender equality. Furthermore, S&P's participation in ceremonies to promote gender equality and eliminate discrimination reflects their proactive stance in fostering an inclusive workplace. By advocating for fair treatment and equal opportunities, S&P communicates its commitment to creating a work environment where diversity is valued, and all employees can thrive. These efforts reinforce the company's dedication to building an inclusive corporate culture that empowers everyone.

Reducing Inequality: S&P Syndicate's initiatives to reduce inequality are well-documented in their content, aligning with SDG 10, which aims to reduce inequality within and among countries. The "S&P Vocational Training: Creating Opportunities for Society" project is a standout initiative that provides vocational training and employment opportunities for disadvantaged groups. By collaborating with the Department of Corrections, S&P offers a second chance to individuals seeking to reintegrate into society. This project highlights the company's role in promoting social equity and reducing disparities. Additionally, S&P supports local farmers by purchasing SDGsPGS-certified organic produce, ensuring fair trade and sustainable practices. By featuring these efforts in their communications, S&P showcases their dedication to social responsibility and economic inclusion, providing tangible support to marginalized communities.

Sustainable Community Development: Aligning with SDG 11, which focuses on making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable, S&P Syndicate's content on sustainable community development highlights several impactful projects. The "S&P Ecosystem Restoration: Returning Value to the Sea" project, for instance, aims to restore marine ecosystems and promote environmental conservation. This initiative is part of S&P's broader strategy to support ecological balance and community well-being. Another notable project is the "Cake A Wish Make A Wish 2024" initiative, where S&P donated 565 pounds of cakes to underprivileged individuals across 22 foundations in Bangkok and surrounding areas. This project brings joy and support to those in need, reflecting the company's commitment to community welfare. The "S&P Food Rescue Project" further demonstrates their dedication to reducing food waste and supporting food security. Additionally, S&P's support for local artisans, such as purchasing 10,000 bags from the Chaba Tie-Dye Community, reinforces their efforts to build strong community relationships and promote sustainable practices. Through these activities, S&P effectively communicates its role in fostering sustainable development and community resilience.

In summary, S&P Syndicate effectively communicates its commitment to the "People" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory through a sustainable communication strategy that includes various initiatives meticulously aligned with relevant SDGs. Their content consistently emphasizes health and well-being, equality and inclusion, reducing inequality, and sustainable community development. By showcasing these efforts, S&P not only enhances its brand image but also

underscores its dedication to creating a positive social impact. This approach helps foster a strong, inclusive, and sustainable community, highlighting the company's role as a leader in corporate social responsibility. Through their strategic communications, S&P demonstrates how businesses can contribute to broader societal goals while achieving their own objectives, setting a benchmark for others in the industry.

Planet

The findings show that S&P Syndicate places significant emphasis on the "Planet" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory. This includes prioritizing the sustainable use of natural resources, preventing and reducing pollution, conserving nature and the environment, and mitigating climate change. The content analysis results are as follows.

Sustainable Use of Natural Resources: S&P Syndicate is dedicated to eco-friendly product design, utilizing biodegradable packaging and utensils, aligning with SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production. Notable initiatives include the Green Restaurant 2023 program, which highlights their commitment to sustainable practices. Additionally, S&P collaborates with BSGF, a subsidiary of Bangchak Corporation, to support the "No Waste Frying" project aimed at reducing the carbon footprint. The introduction of vegetarian menus further demonstrates their dedication to environmentally conscious offerings.

In their pursuit of environmentally friendly products, S&P sources ingredients from sustainable farms, supporting SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production. A key example is their support for farmers in Nan by purchasing SDGsPGS-certified organic oranges, ensuring the produce is clean, chemical-free, and traceable. This initiative not only promotes sustainable agriculture but also supports local farmers, reinforcing S&P's commitment to environmental sustainability.

Pollution Prevention and Reduction: S&P Syndicate is actively engaged in pollution prevention and reduction initiatives, aligning with SDG 13: Climate Action and SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production. In their efforts to use renewable energy in production, S&P has installed solar panels and adopted energy-efficient appliances. A significant step towards this goal is their drive towards Net Zero, highlighted by the launch of the first eco-friendly 'S&P EV Truck' and the installation of 'Solar Roof' systems at four additional locations. These initiatives are part of the Green Restaurant 2023 program, demonstrating their commitment to reducing their environmental footprint. S&P also implements comprehensive waste management and recycling initiatives. They have developed a robust recycling program and compost organic waste to minimize environmental impact. Collaborating with BSGF, a subsidiary of Bangchak Corporation, S&P supports the "No Waste Frying" project, further reducing their carbon footprint. Additionally, the S&P Food Rescue Project plays a crucial role in their sustainability efforts, with S&P receiving the SOS Awards 2022 for OUTSTANDING FOOD RESCUE AWARD - RESTAURANT CHAIN. These efforts showcase S&P's dedication to responsible consumption and production, reinforcing their commitment to environmental sustainability.

Conservation of Nature and Environment: S&P Syndicate strongly emphasizes on the conservation of nature and the environment, aligning their efforts with SDG 15: Life on Land and SDG 14: Life Below Water.

In their commitment to forest and natural area conservation, S&P supports reforestation projects and purchases carbon offsets. They demonstrate this by supporting farmers in Nan and purchasing SDGsPGS-certified organic oranges. This initiative ensures the produce is clean, chemical-free, and traceable, promoting sustainable agricultural practices and contributing to land conservation. Moreover, S&P is actively involved in supporting marine life protection projects. They avoid using ingredients that contribute to overfishing and promote sustainable seafood practices. A notable initiative is the 'S&P Ecosystem Restoration: Returning Value to the Sea' project, which underscores their dedication to restoring and protecting marine ecosystems. These efforts collectively reflect S&P's commitment to conserving nature and the environment, ensuring their operations support the health of terrestrial and marine ecosystems.

Climate Change Mitigation: S&P Syndicate is committed to climate change mitigation through innovative practices and raising awareness, aligning with SDG 13: Climate Action. In their innovation to address climate change, S&P has developed menus that reduce the carbon footprint, including plant-based options. This effort is recognized by the Carbon Footprint Label certification awarded to S&P. Furthermore, their collaboration with BSGF, a subsidiary of Bangchak Corporation, supports the "No Waste Frying" project aimed at reducing the carbon footprint. S&P's drive towards Net Zero is exemplified by launching the first eco-friendly 'S&P EV Truck' and installing 'Solar Roof' systems at four additional locations. These initiatives are part of the Green Restaurant 2023 program and include the introduction of vegetarian menus, further demonstrating their dedication to environmentally sustainable practices. S&P also focuses on raising awareness about climate change by educating customers on the environmental impact of their food choices. They create infographic content to educate customers, particularly on occasions such as World Environment Day. This educational approach helps to inform and engage customers in S&P's climate action initiatives, fostering a greater understanding of the importance of reducing carbon footprints and supporting sustainable practices.

On the "Planet" aspect, S&P Syndicate uses a comprehensive sustainable communication strategy to convey their commitment to the "Planet" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory. They emphasize sustainable use of natural resources through eco-friendly product designs, such as biodegradable packaging, and initiatives like the Green Restaurant 2023 program and the "No Waste Frying" project. Pollution prevention is highlighted by showcasing renewable energy efforts, such as solar panel installations and the eco-friendly 'S&P EV Truck,' alongside comprehensive waste management programs. Conservation efforts are communicated through projects like 'S&P Ecosystem Restoration: Returning Value to the Sea' and support for sustainable farming. Climate change mitigation is addressed through the development of plant-based menus, the drive towards Net Zero, and educational content on environmental impacts. This strategy effectively showcases S&P's dedication to environmental sustainability and responsible consumption and production.

Profit

The findings show that S&P Syndicate employs a sustainability communication strategy focused on the "Profit" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory. This strategy prioritizes the sustainable use of natural resources, job creation and quality employment, innovation and technology development, and fostering partnerships and collaboration. The content analysis results are as follows.

Sustainable Economic Growth: S&P Syndicate emphasizes creating unique, high-quality dining experiences that attract customers, aligning with SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth. The company bases its strong foundation on good corporate governance principles, ensuring sustainable growth by adhering to the principles of "Quality, Value, Virtue." This commitment to excellence has been recognized through winning the "Marketeer No.1 Brand Thailand 2023" award in the Bakery Shop category, marking their fourth consecutive year as a consumer favorite.

S&P Syndicate is dedicated to long-term business development by investing in technology and processes that enhance efficiency and sustainability, supporting SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth. The company is driving towards Net Zero with initiatives such as launching the first eco-friendly 'S&P EV Truck' and installing 'Solar Roof' systems at four additional locations. These efforts have earned S&P an "A" rating in the SET ESG Rating for sustainability in 2023, highlighting their commitment to sustainable business practices and long-term growth.

Job Creation and Quality Employment: S&P Syndicate is committed to maintaining high standards of workplace safety and ergonomics, aligning with SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth. Through initiatives like the Green Restaurant 2023, the company ensures a safe and healthy working environment for its employees. This focus on safety and ergonomics not only enhances employee well-being but also contributes to overall productivity and job satisfaction, reinforcing S&P's dedication to providing quality employment and fostering a positive work culture.

Innovation and Technology Development: S&P Syndicate showcases technologies that reduce energy and water usage, aligning with SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure. The company drives towards Net Zero by launching the first eco-friendly 'S&P EV Truck' and installing 'Solar Roof' systems at four additional locations. These eco-friendly innovations demonstrate S&P's dedication to sustainability and environmental responsibility, ensuring that their operations are both efficient and environmentally friendly.

Partnerships and Collaboration: S&P Syndicate is dedicated to building-wide business networks that focus on sustainable practices, aligning with SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals. A notable example of this commitment is S&P's participation in the MOU Signing Ceremony for the "Plastic Footprint Reduction Project." This initiative is part of the SEA Circular Program of UNEP, sponsored by the Government of the Kingdom of Sweden and organized by the Solid Waste Management Association (Thailand) (SWAT). By joining industry groups and participating in collaborative projects, S&P Syndicate reinforces its dedication to sustainability through strategic partnerships and collective action.

S&P Syndicate employs a sustainability communication strategy focused on the "Profit" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory, prioritizing sustainable use of natural resources, job creation and quality employment, innovation and technology development, and partnerships and collaboration. They emphasize high-quality dining experiences and long-term growth, highlighted by awards like

the "Marketeer No.1 Brand Thailand 2023." Initiatives such as the eco-friendly 'S&P EV Truck' and 'Solar Roof' installations showcase their commitment to efficiency and sustainability. S&P maintains high workplace safety standards through programs like Green Restaurant 2023 and fosters industry collaboration, exemplified by their participation in the SEA Circular Program's "Plastic Footprint Reduction Project." These efforts align with SDGs 8, 9, and 17, demonstrating S&P's dedication to sustainable business practices.

Message Tone Analysis

Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC)

The findings indicate that S&P Syndicate consistently communicates its sustainability message with keywords such as "Quality Value and Virtue" and "The Pursuit of Strength and Growth." These themes are consistently reflected across their website and social media platforms, emphasizing the importance of quality and virtue in its operations and aligning its growth strategies with sustainable practices. The brand utilizes various communication tools, including videos, images, and social media content, to disseminate its sustainability messages. Their Facebook posts are particularly rich in sustainability content, showcasing their efforts and achievements. However, a notable absence of sustainability-related content on their Instagram account indicates a gap in their communication strategy on this platform. Integration of communication channels is evident in S&P Syndicate's strategy, with cross-referencing between their website and social media platforms, ensuring a cohesive and unified message across different channels.

Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM)

In analyzing the sustainability communication strategies of S&P Syndicate through the lens of the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM), distinct approaches can be observed in their use of the central and peripheral routes to persuasion. S&P Syndicate employs the central route by providing detailed and substantial information about their sustainability practices, including presenting logical arguments and factual data, particularly focusing on the environmental and social impacts of their operations. This approach aims to engage the audience on a cognitive level, encouraging them to think critically about the brand's sustainability efforts. In addition to the central route, S&P Syndicate also utilizes the peripheral route by incorporating engaging visuals and superficial cues. Attractive images and videos capture the audience's attention, while emotional appeals are made by displaying stories and testimonials from customers or employees. These elements create an emotional connection with the audience, complementing the more rational arguments presented through the central route.

Narrative

Narrative theory offers valuable insights into the storytelling techniques employed to effectively engage audiences and promote sustainability initiatives. This theory emphasizes compelling narratives that can influence public perception and behavior by creating emotional connections with the audience.

The findings indicate that S&P Syndicate leverages narrative strategies to highlight the initiatives and achievements led by its management team, emphasizing its leadership in sustainable

practices. Through emotional appeals, particularly in the areas of community involvement and charitable activities, S&P fosters a sense of solidarity and collective responsibility among its stakeholders.

These narratives not only promote active participation in sustainability efforts but also evoke feelings of gratitude, responsibility, and commitment to sustainable cooperation. By utilizing the peripheral route of persuasion, S&P effectively captures attention and fosters a positive association with its brand, ultimately reinforcing its role as a socially responsible corporation committed to sustainable development. This approach illustrates how strategic storytelling can be a powerful tool in aligning corporate objectives with broader societal goals, thereby enhancing both engagement and impact. S&P engages its audience through formal visuals and superficial cues, positioning itself as a community benefactor and a responsible corporate entity with an attractive image. However, there is only a slight connection between the information presented and the corporate brand, suggesting room for a stronger alignment in their communication strategy.

Sustainability Communication Strategies of Global Brand Restaurants on Social Media and Websites: “Minor Food”.

This part studies how Global brand restaurants communicate sustainability on social media and websites, focusing on “Minor Food”. The research results are presented in three parts as follows.

Content themes Analysis

The Three Bottom Line (People, Planet, Profit)

The findings indicate that Minor Food has shown unwavering dedication to sustainable development, prioritizing the three bottom lines: People, Planet, and Profit. This approach emphasizes social responsibility, environmental stewardship, and economic viability. By aligning their initiatives with key Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Minor Food integrates these principles into their core operations. This section explores how Minor Food effectively communicates its commitment to these values through various content and communication strategies, underscoring their role as a socially responsible corporation.

People. The findings show that Minor Food particularly focuses on the "People" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory, emphasizing health and well-being, equality and inclusion, reducing inequality, and sustainable community development. The content analysis results are as follows.

Health and Well-being: Minor Food is dedicated to enhancing employee health and well-being through various initiatives that align with Sustainable Development Goal 3, which focuses on good health and well-being. They offer programs that emphasize achieving a harmonious work-life balance with the guidance of Dr. Phinyo Rattanapan, Thailand's Ikigai pioneer. Additionally, Minor Food provides group exercise sessions, yoga classes, and 'Minor Talks' on topics such as health prevention and anti-aging to promote overall wellness. These efforts are complemented by 'Social Lunch' networking and learning activities, all with a strong emphasis on occupational health and safety, ensuring a safe and supportive workplace environment. The commitment to community health is exemplified by the Minor Care Campaign, which donates proceeds from special menu items to support the construction of the Siriraj Center of Excellence in Geriatric Medicine. This initiative highlights their dedication to contributing to broader societal health and well-being.

Customer Health: In response to growing demands for environmentally friendly and healthy products, Minor Food has committed that by 2024, all its brands will offer at least one new sustainable or healthy menu item. In 2022, five out of ten Minor Food brands launched a total of 59 meals, including plant-based, vegan, and vegetarian dishes. Furthermore, Minor Food has committed to a global cage-free initiative, ensuring higher animal welfare standards across their supply chain.

Employee Training and Education: Minor Food invests significantly in employee training and education to foster a skilled and knowledgeable workforce, aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 4, which emphasizes quality education. Programs such as the Future Leaders Accelerator Program, in partnership with GP Strategies, and M-LEAD, Minor's Executive Leadership Acceleration Program, are designed to develop leadership capabilities. Additional initiatives include the Sizzler Master Competition, workshops on effective storytelling led by Dr. Parida Manomaiphikul, and 'Minor Live Talk' events on trending topics like AI technology. Through the 'Horizon' program, in collaboration with Thammasat Consulting Networking and Coaching Center, employees are equipped with adaptive leadership and innovation skills. The 2023 Minor Food Manager Conference further reinforces their commitment to leadership and growth.

Scholarships and Skill Development in the Community: Minor Food supports educational advancement and skill development in the community through substantial scholarship programs and strategic partnerships, also aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 4. Together with the Heinecke Foundation, they have awarded over 9.4 million baht in scholarships to 1,444 students, benefiting local communities and children of junior-level staff. The Heinecke Foundation Scholarship has provided educational support to over 9,800 children. Minor Food also collaborates with academic institutions such as Tsinghua University, Thammasat University, Bangkok University, Mahidol University International College, Srinakharinwirot University, and Khonkaen University to offer study visits, competitions, and career development programs. These partnerships empower youth, enhance professional development, and prepare future leaders, driving regional success.

Equality and Inclusion: Promoting diversity in the workplace, Minor Food Group aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 5, which emphasizes gender equality. They have been certified as a "Great Place to Work" from April 2024 to April 2025. Additionally, Minor Food promotes the value and involvement of women, especially during International Women's Day month, showcasing their commitment to gender equality.

Reducing Inequality: Minor Food Group is committed to reducing inequality by creating employment opportunities for disadvantaged groups, aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 10. They have received an award from the Thai Health Promotion Foundation and the Social Innovation Foundation for their efforts in developing careers and employment for youth with disabilities. Additionally, Minor Food has proudly supported over 350 people with disabilities through various employment opportunities. Their support for local community development is demonstrated by initiatives like Swensen's Durian Town, a collaboration with the Chanthaburi Chamber of Commerce.

Sustainable Community Development: Aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 11, which focuses on sustainable cities and communities, Minor Food Group engages in various community service activities. The Minor Run in the Park exceeded its target distance, allowing the company to reach its highest donation goal. The funds were used to purchase essential items for the Duang Prateep Foundation. Additionally, Minor Food Group has enhanced the quality of life for Thai students at the College of Agriculture and Technology Bang Sai Arts and Crafts Center by improving facilities, dormitories, and vegetable gardens and organizing online donations for school development.

Building strong community relationships, Minor Food Group has introduced over 960 students to Minor Corporate University, marking the beginning of their career journey within Minor's businesses, including Minor Hotels, Minor Food, and Minor Lifestyle, through their bilateral program. The Chief People Officer of Minor International received a certificate and honorary badge from Police General Permpoon Chidchob, the Minister of Education, demonstrating her dedication and outstanding contribution to educational development through Minor's initiative programs aligned with the ministry's development goals. Additionally, Minor held a certificate ceremony for 980 students from 55 colleges and three universities graduating from the Minor Corporate University program in 2023. This program, aligned with their mission 'Minor Build People, People Build Nation', prioritizes developing in-demand skills for students. The Minor Franchise Academy, in partnership with Thammasat University, and collaborations with other universities, including Bangkok University, Mahidol University International College, Srinakharinwirot University, and Khonkaen University, further demonstrate Minor Food Group's commitment to sustainable community development. These initiatives are designed to empower youth, enhance professional development, and foster strong community relationships, driving both personal and regional success.

Minor Food employs a comprehensive sustainable communication strategy focusing on the "People" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory. This includes enhancing employee health and well-being through programs like group exercises, yoga classes, and 'Minor Talks' on health topics, as well as supporting community health initiatives such as the Minor Care Campaign. The company addresses customer health by introducing sustainable and healthy menu options and committing to a global cage-free initiative. Employee training and education are prioritized through leadership programs like the Future Leaders Accelerator Program and partnerships with academic institutions, fostering professional growth and development. Scholarship programs and skill development initiatives benefit local communities, emphasizing Minor Food's dedication to educational advancement. Additionally, Minor Food promotes diversity in the workplace, supports employment opportunities for disadvantaged groups, and engages in sustainable community development activities like the Minor Run in the Park and collaborations with universities. These efforts are aligned with relevant Sustainable Development Goals, demonstrating Minor Food's commitment to social responsibility, community engagement, and long-term sustainability.

Planet. The findings show that Minor Food places a strong focus on the "Planet" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory. This involves prioritizing the sustainable use of natural resources,

preventing and reducing pollution, conserving nature and the environment, and mitigating climate change. The content analysis results are as follows.

Sustainable Use of Natural Resources: Minor Food emphasizes eco-friendly product design by using biodegradable packaging and utensils, aligning with SDG 12 for Responsible Consumption and Production. By 2024, all Minor Food brands will offer at least one new sustainable or healthy menu item in response to growing customer demands for environmentally friendly and healthy products. In 2022, five out of ten Minor Food brands introduced a total of 59 meals to the market, including plant-based, vegan, and vegetarian dishes. The company also focuses on reducing food loss and waste in its supply chain and encourages customers to participate in sustainability efforts, as seen in Swensen's Earth Day Campaign, where customers brought their own containers to receive ice cream with a special promotion. For the development of environmentally friendly products, Minor Food sources ingredients from sustainable farms and implements a sustainable supply chain program. This includes procuring sustainable and certified materials from trusted sources and committing to a global cage-free initiative. In terms of water conservation, Minor Food is dedicated to water stewardship, ensuring that wastewater from their operations meets or exceeds local regulatory standards.

Pollution Prevention and Reduction: Minor Food actively engages in pollution prevention and reduction by using renewable energy in production. This includes installing solar panels and using energy-efficient appliances, aligning with SDG 13 for Climate Action. The company has a comprehensive plan for achieving Net Zero and, in 2023, invested over Baht 362 million in energy efficiency initiatives, reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 3,519 tons. Additionally, Minor Food converts used cooking oil into biodiesel and conducts sustainability workshops for board members, senior management, and team members with a pledge to become a Net-zero Carbon organization by 2050. For waste management and recycling, Minor Food implements comprehensive recycling programs and composts organic waste. They focus on reducing food loss and waste in their supply chain and have innovative partnerships, such as with CIRCULAR, to create products like caps and bucket caps made from recycled Sizzler staff uniforms.

Conservation of Nature and Environment: Minor Food supports forest and natural area conservation by participating in reforestation projects and purchasing carbon offsets, aligning with SDG 15 for Life on Land. The company is also dedicated to supporting marine life protection projects by avoiding ingredients that contribute to overfishing and promoting sustainable seafood. For example, in Phuket, Thailand, Minor Food supported the Mai Khao Marine Turtle Foundation (MKMTF) in conserving endangered sea turtles, resulting in the release of over 120 turtles back to the sea in 2023.

Climate Change Mitigation: Minor Food addresses climate change through innovation by developing menus that reduce the carbon footprint, such as plant-based options, aligning with SDG 13 for Climate Action. In 2023, Minor Food's energy efficiency initiatives, backed by an investment of over Baht 362 million, resulted in a significant reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. The company is committed to introducing at least one new sustainable or healthy menu item across all its brands by 2024, responding to customer demands for environmentally friendly products. Additionally, Minor Food raises awareness about climate change by educating customers on the

environmental impact of their food choices through content for World Wildlife Day and World Food Day.

In Summary, Minor Food employs a comprehensive sustainable communication strategy focusing on the "Planet" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory. This strategy emphasizes the sustainable use of natural resources, pollution prevention and reduction, conservation of nature and the environment, and climate change mitigation. They showcase their commitment through initiatives like eco-friendly product designs, sustainable menu options, and reducing food waste. Their sustainable supply chain practices and water conservation efforts further highlight their dedication to responsible resource use. Minor Food invests in renewable energy and energy-efficient technologies, aiming for Net Zero carbon emissions by 2050. Their waste management and recycling programs, such as partnerships with CIRCULAR, demonstrate a proactive approach to reducing environmental impact. Conservation efforts include supporting reforestation projects and marine life protection, such as the Mai Khao Marine Turtle Foundation. To address climate change, Minor Food develops low-carbon menu options and educates customers on the environmental impact of their choices through events like World Wildlife Day and World Food Day. By aligning with key Sustainable Development Goals, Minor Food integrates environmental stewardship into their core operations and effectively communicates their leadership in sustainable business practices.

Profit. The findings indicate that Minor Food employs a sustainability communication strategy focused on the "Profit" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory. This strategy prioritizes the sustainable use of natural resources, job creation and quality employment, innovation, and technology development, and fostering partnerships and collaboration. The content analysis results are as follows.

Sustainable Economic Growth: Minor Food demonstrates its commitment to sustainable economic growth by developing valuable products and services that create unique, high-quality dining experiences, aligning with SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth. Their strong financial performance in Q3 2023, various industry awards, and successful franchise agreements highlight this commitment. For instance, The Coffee Club Thailand won a Silver Award at the Marketing Award of Thailand 2023, and Burger King Thailand received a gold award for event marketing at the 2023 Marketing Excellence Awards. Furthermore, Swensen's received the Best Restaurant Influencer Campaign award at the 2023 Thailand Influencer Awards for the second consecutive year. These accolades reflect Minor Food's focus on enhancing customer experiences and maintaining high standards of service and quality. In terms of long-term business development, Minor Food invests in technology and processes that improve efficiency and sustainability. This includes receiving the AMCHAM Corporate Social Impact Award at the platinum level and a gold award at the 2023 HR Excellence Awards in the Talent Management category. These recognitions underscore Minor Food's dedication to creating sustainable value for all stakeholders.

Job Creation and Quality Employment: Minor Food is dedicated to creating new jobs and enhancing employee skills, aligning with SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth. Programs like the Future Leaders Accelerator Program, in partnership with GP Strategies, and workshops on

effective storytelling led by experts like Dr. Parida Manomaiphikul highlight their focus on employee development. Additionally, initiatives such as the Sizzler Master Competition, 'Minor Live Talk' events on AI technology, and collaborations with culinary schools like Dong Fang Culinary School in China demonstrate their commitment to developing skilled human capital and sustaining business continuity through high-performance management.

Innovation and Technology Development: Minor Food invests in eco-friendly innovations to reduce energy and water usage, aligning with SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure. The company is committed to water stewardship, ensuring that its wastewater meets or exceeds local regulatory standards, showcasing its dedication to environmental sustainability.

Partnerships and Collaboration: Minor Food actively builds wide business networks for sustainability by joining industry groups focused on sustainable practices, aligning with SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals. This includes signing an MOU with Srinakharinwirot University to foster collaboration in educational expansion and professional development and partnering with Thammasat University for the Minor Franchise Academy. Additionally, collaborations with institutions like Bangkok University and Mahidol University International College aim to empower youth and support career growth through initiatives like the 'New Product Concept' competition and other educational programs. These partnerships not only strengthen Minor Food's strategic alliances but also contribute to regional success and sustainable development.

Minor Food employs a sustainable communication strategy focused on the "Profit" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory. This strategy includes developing high-quality dining experiences, being recognized through various industry awards, and investing in technology to improve efficiency and sustainability, as evidenced by their accolades like the AMCHAM Corporate Social Impact Award. They prioritize job creation and employee skill enhancement through programs like the Future Leaders Accelerator and partnerships with culinary schools. Additionally, Minor Food invests in eco-friendly innovations, particularly in water stewardship, to align with industry standards. Their extensive collaborations with academic institutions for educational expansion and professional development underscore their commitment to sustainability. By integrating these initiatives into their core operations, Minor Food effectively communicates its role as a leader in sustainable business practices, contributing to economic growth, environmental stewardship, and community development.

Message Tone Analysis

Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC)

The findings show that Minor Food consistently communicates its sustainability message through key phrases such as "Minor is More," "People Build Brands," "Great Place to Work," "Passion for Growth," and "Learning @Minor." These themes are prominently featured across their website and social media platforms, ensuring a cohesive and recognizable sustainability narrative. The company effectively coordinates various communication tools by utilizing videos, images, and social media content across platforms like Facebook and Instagram. This multimedia approach enhances engagement and ensures that their sustainability efforts are vividly and compellingly presented to their audience. Minor Food demonstrates strong integration of their communication channels by prominently displaying their website URL and Facebook name on the first page of their Instagram

account. This strategy ensures seamless navigation for users between different platforms, reinforcing their sustainability message consistently across all channels.

Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM)

The findings show that Minor Food employs the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) to communicate its sustainability practices through both central and peripheral routes. The company provides detailed and substantial information about its sustainability practices, offering in-depth insights into their initiatives. This includes logical arguments and factual data on the environmental and social impacts of their operations. By presenting this detailed information, Minor Food aims to engage its audience on a cognitive level, encouraging them to critically evaluate their sustainability efforts.

Alongside the central route, Minor Food utilizes engaging visuals and superficial cues to capture the audience's attention. Attractive images and videos are used extensively to make its sustainability message more appealing. Emotional appeals are also a key component of their strategy. For example, Swensen's employees share heartfelt moments with their mothers on Mother's Day, and customer stories are displayed to create a personal connection with the audience. These elements help to evoke emotions and build a relatable and engaging narrative around Minor Food's sustainability initiatives.

Narrative

The findings indicate that providing detailed information about a company's achievements and the strategies employed by its people, as well as its various activities, plays a crucial role in encouraging a wider range of stakeholders to support and engage with the company's sustainability efforts. By transparently sharing its successes, milestones, and strategic approaches, the company not only informs but also inspires its audience, fostering a sense of trust and credibility. This comprehensive communication strategy enables stakeholders—including employees, customers, partners, and the broader community—to better understand and appreciate the company's commitment to sustainable development. Additionally, utilizing the peripheral route of persuasion, the company effectively evokes a sense of pride and passion in these achievements among employees and stakeholders.

This emotional engagement enhances stakeholders' connection to the company's mission and values, further motivating them to actively participate in and advocate for its sustainability initiatives. By highlighting accomplishments and recognizing the collective contributions of its workforce and partners, the company reinforces a positive organizational culture and solidifies its reputation as a leader in corporate social responsibility. Consequently, this approach not only strengthens internal morale and loyalty but also extends the company's influence and impact in promoting sustainable practices within the wider community. Minor Food employs storytelling and professional imagery, using business-style terminology that is vividly and compellingly presented to their audience. This approach reflects the connection between the organization's purpose, stakeholder engagement, and the integration of its corporate brand.

The Comparative Analysis of Sustainability Communication Strategies of Thai and Global Brand Restaurants on Social Media and Websites

This section compares the sustainability communication strategies between the Thai restaurant “S&P Syndicate” and the global brand “Minor Food” as they communicate sustainability on social media and websites. The research results are presented in three parts as follows.

Content themes Comparative Analysis

The Three Bottom Line (People, Planet, Profit)

Comparative Analysis: The Three Bottom Line (People, Planet, Profit) between Thai Brand Restaurant: S&P Syndicate and Global Brand Restaurant Minor Food in the [Table 1](#).

Table 1

Content Themes Analysis of the Three Bottom Line (People, Planet, Profit) Between Thai Brand Restaurant: S&P Syndicate and Global Brand Restaurant Minor Food

Criteria	Thai Brand Restaurant : S&P Syndicate	Global Brand Restaurant: Minor Food
People	S&P Syndicate focuses on enhancing employee health and well-being through programs such as group exercises, yoga classes, and health talks. They support community health initiatives like the Minor Care Campaign, which funds medical facilities. Customer health is addressed by offering sustainable and healthy menu options. They also prioritize employee training and education through various leadership programs and workshops, and they support scholarships and skill development in the community.	Minor Food emphasizes human development, focusing on employee health with programs like work-life balance sessions, exercise activities, and health talks. They engage in community health initiatives by supporting medical centers through campaigns. For customer health, they commit to offering sustainable menu options and promoting a global cage-free commitment. Employee development is furthered through leadership programs, culinary training, and partnerships with educational institutions, and they provide substantial scholarships and skill development opportunities for community members.
Planet	S&P Syndicate places a strong emphasis on environmental sustainability. They focus on eco-friendly product designs, the use of biodegradable packaging, and sustainable sourcing of ingredients. They implement comprehensive recycling and waste management programs and engage in pollution prevention through energy-efficient practices. Additionally, they participate in conservation projects and support marine life protection initiatives.	Minor Food prioritizes the sustainable use of natural resources, pollution prevention, and environmental conservation. They adopt eco-friendly innovations like biodegradable packaging and energy-efficient technologies. They implement water conservation measures and ensure wastewater meets regulatory standards. Minor Food is committed to reducing their carbon footprint through initiatives like the Net Zero plan and converting used cooking oil to biodiesel. They also participate in reforestation projects and marine conservation efforts.

Criteria	Thai Brand Restaurant : S&P Syndicate	Global Brand Restaurant: Minor Food
Profit	S&P Syndicate's approach to sustainable economic growth includes developing high-quality dining experiences and investing in long-term business development. They emphasize job creation and quality employment through training programs and leadership development. Innovation and technology development are highlighted by their investments in eco-friendly technologies and sustainable practices. They also foster partnerships and collaboration with industry groups and educational institutions.	Minor Food's profit strategy focuses on sustainable economic growth by developing valuable products and services recognized through various industry awards. They invest in technology and processes to improve efficiency and sustainability. Job creation and quality employment are prioritized through leadership programs and culinary training partnerships. Innovation and technology development include investments in water conservation and energy-efficient technologies. They build extensive business networks for sustainability by partnering with academic institutions and industry groups for educational expansion and professional development.

Both S&P Syndicate and Minor Food demonstrate a strong commitment to the Three Bottom Line theory, but they emphasize different aspects within their sustainability strategies. S&P Syndicate focuses more on environmental sustainability, with extensive efforts in eco-friendly practices and conservation projects. In contrast, Minor Food emphasizes human development, investing heavily in employee and community growth through education, training, and health initiatives. Both brands prioritize sustainable economic growth and responsible business practices, but Minor Food's approach is more balanced, integrating human development with environmental stewardship and innovative business practices. Overall, both S&P Syndicate and Minor Food effectively integrate the principles of the Three Bottom Line into their operations, reflecting their roles as leaders in sustainable business practices.

Message Tone Analysis

Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC)

Comparative Analysis: Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) between S&P Syndicate and Minor Food in [Table 2](#).

Table 2

Message Tone Comparative Analysis: Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) between Thai Brand Restaurant: S&P Syndicate And Global Brand Restaurant Minor Food

Criteria	Thai Brand Restaurant: S&P Syndicate	Global Brand Restaurant: Minor Food
Consistency of Sustainability Message	S&P Syndicate maintains a consistent sustainability message through its key themes of "Quality, Value, and Virtue" and "The Pursuit of Strength and Growth." These themes are consistently presented across their website and social media platforms, reinforcing their commitment to sustainable practices.	Minor Food communicates a consistent sustainability message through key phrases such as "Minor is More," "People Build Brands," "Great Place to Work," "Passion for Growth," and "Learning @Minor." These themes are prominently featured on their website and social media platforms, ensuring a cohesive narrative on sustainability. The key messages indicate a strong focus on human development.

Criteria	Thai Brand Restaurant: S&P Syndicate	Global Brand Restaurant: Minor Food
Coordination of Communication Tools	S&P Syndicate utilizes a variety of communication tools, including videos, images, and social media content. They prominently use Facebook to share their sustainability initiatives but have less presence on platforms like Instagram for sustainability content.	Minor Food effectively coordinates various communication tools, including videos, images, and social media content across platforms like Facebook and Instagram. This multimedia approach enhances engagement and ensures their sustainability efforts are vividly and compellingly presented to their audience.
Integration of Channels	There is a strong integration of communication channels at S&P Syndicate, with frequent cross-referencing between their website and social media platforms. This ensures a seamless and cohesive delivery of their sustainability message across different media.	Minor Food demonstrates strong integration of their communication channels by prominently displaying their website URL and Facebook name on the first page of their Instagram account. This strategy ensures seamless navigation for users between different platforms, reinforcing their sustainability message consistently across all channels.

In Summary, Both S&P Syndicate and Minor Food prioritize the consistency of their sustainability messages, although they use different themes to convey their commitments. S&P Syndicate focuses on "Quality, Value, and Virtue," highlighting a strong emphasis on environmental sustainability. In contrast, Minor Food uses phrases like "Minor is More" and "People Build Brands," underscoring their focus on human development. In terms of coordination of communication tools, Minor Food appears to utilize a wider range of multimedia content across more social media platforms than S&P Syndicate, which primarily uses Facebook. When it comes to the integration of channels, both companies show strong practices, but Minor Food's approach of prominently linking their platforms ensures a more seamless user experience. Overall, both brands effectively use IMC strategies to communicate their sustainability efforts. S&P Syndicate focuses on environmental aspects, while Minor Food emphasizes human development, demonstrating how each brand tailors its communication strategy to its core sustainability priorities.

Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM)

Comparative Analysis: Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) between Thai Brand Restaurant: S&P Syndicate and Global Brand Restaurant Minor Food in [Table 3](#).

Both S&P Syndicate and Minor Food effectively utilize the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) to communicate their sustainability practices through both central and peripheral routes. S&P Syndicate focuses on providing detailed and substantial information about their sustainability initiatives, emphasizing logical arguments and factual data. Their approach is geared towards engaging the audience cognitively to foster a critical evaluation of their environmental and social impacts. Similarly, Minor Food offers in-depth information about their sustainability efforts, presenting logical arguments and factual data to engage their audience on a cognitive level, encouraging a deeper understanding and critical assessment of their practices. On the peripheral

route, S&P Syndicate uses engaging visuals and emotional appeals to capture the audience's attention.

Table 3

Comparative Analysis: Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) between Thai Brand Restaurant: S&P Syndicate and Global Brand Restaurant Minor Food

Criteria	Thai Brand Restaurant : S&P Syndicate	Global Brand Restaurant: Minor Food
Central Route	S&P Syndicate uses the central route to communicate detailed and substantial information about their sustainability practices. They provide in-depth details on their initiatives, emphasizing logical arguments and factual data on environmental and social impacts. This approach aims to engage the audience cognitively, encouraging them to critically evaluate S&P's sustainability efforts.	Minor Food employs the central route by providing detailed and substantial information about their sustainability practices. They offer in-depth insights into their initiatives, including logical arguments and factual data on environmental and social impacts. This method aims to engage their audience on a cognitive level, encouraging a deeper understanding and critical evaluation of their sustainability efforts.
Peripheral Route	S&P Syndicate also employs the peripheral route by using engaging visuals and superficial cues to capture attention. Attractive images and videos are used to make their sustainability message more appealing. Emotional appeals, such as customer testimonials and stories, are utilized to create a personal connection with the audience, enhancing the overall impact of their communication.	In addition to the central route, Minor Food uses the peripheral route by incorporating engaging visuals and superficial cues. They use attractive images and videos extensively to make their sustainability message more compelling. Emotional appeals are a significant part of their strategy, with campaigns like Swensen's employees sharing heartfelt moments with their mothers on Mother's Day and customer stories being displayed to create a relatable and engaging narrative.

They leverage attractive images and videos to enhance the appeal of their sustainability message, along with customer testimonials and stories to create a personal connection. Minor Food employs a similar strategy with extensive use of engaging visuals and emotional appeals. Their campaigns, such as Swensen's Mother's Day stories, utilize attractive images and customer narratives to build a relatable and emotionally engaging narrative around their sustainability initiatives. Overall, both S&P Syndicate and Minor Food use the ELM framework effectively to communicate their sustainability practices. S&P Syndicate leans slightly more towards emphasizing detailed information and logical arguments, whereas Minor Food balances this with a stronger emphasis on engaging visuals and emotional appeals, making their sustainability message both informative and compelling.

Narrative

Comparative Analysis: Narrative between Thai Brand Restaurant: S&P Syndicate and Global Brand Restaurant Minor Food in [Table 4](#).

Table 4

Comparative Analysis: Narrative between Thai Brand Restaurant: S&P Syndicate and Global Brand Restaurant Minor Food

Criteria	Thai Brand Restaurant : S&P Syndicate	Global Brand Restaurant: Minor Food
Narrative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initiatives and achievements by the leader and management team • Emotional appeals with community and charity to support and participate in sustainability efforts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detailed information on company's achievements, strategies by people, and activity • Encourages a wider range of stakeholders to support and engage with the company's efforts.
Storytelling and image	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging formal visuals and superficial cues • Be a community Giver and responsible corporate as attractive image • Slightly connection between information and corporate brand 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional image and business-style terminology are vividly and compellingly presented to their audience. • Reflects the connection of organization's purpose, engagement, and combination of corporate brand

The comparative analysis between the Thai brand restaurant S&P Syndicate and the global brand restaurant Minor Food, as illustrated in [Table 3](#), highlights distinct approaches in their narrative and storytelling strategies. S&P Syndicate focuses on narratives that emphasize the initiatives and achievements of its leaders and management team, employing emotional appeals centered around community involvement and charitable efforts to foster participation in sustainability initiatives. In terms of storytelling and imagery, S&P Syndicate utilizes formal visuals and superficial cues to project an image of a community benefactor and a responsible corporate entity. However, there appears to be only a slight connection between the information presented and the corporate brand, indicating potential gaps in integrating their messaging with their brand identity.

In contrast, Minor Food takes a more comprehensive approach by providing detailed information about the company's achievements, strategies, and activities. This strategy encourages a wider range of stakeholders to support and engage with the company's efforts. The storytelling and imagery used by Minor Food are characterized by a professional image and business-style terminology that is vividly and compellingly presented to their audience. This approach effectively reflects the organization's purpose and fosters a strong connection between stakeholder engagement and the integration of the corporate brand. Consequently, Minor Food's narrative strategy demonstrates a more cohesive and aligned communication approach compared to S&P Syndicate, ensuring that their brand identity is consistently reinforced through their narratives and engagement efforts.

Discussion and Conclusion

Summary of results

This section summarizes the sustainability communication strategies of S&P Syndicate and Minor Food, highlighting their distinct approaches and thematic focuses. S&P Syndicate primarily centers its communication on the "Planet" aspect of the Triple Bottom Line, emphasizing health, equality, and sustainable community development through localized initiatives, such as employee health insurance, gender equality efforts, vocational training, and community-based environmental

projects. In contrast, Minor Food focuses on the "People" and "Profit" aspects, promoting people development, innovative practices, and global impact through comprehensive health programs, educational partnerships, and technological innovations. The comparative analysis reveals that while S&P Syndicate's messaging is rooted in local engagement and social responsibility, Minor Food adopts a broader, more globally-oriented approach, integrating diverse stakeholder perspectives. Both brands utilize the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) to convey their messages, but with differing emphases; S&P Syndicate relies on detailed content and emotional appeals, whereas Minor Food combines logical arguments with engaging narratives across multiple platforms. These findings illustrate how each brand effectively communicates its sustainability efforts, offering valuable insights for enhancing sustainability messaging and stakeholder engagement.

Content themes

Content Themes of S&P Syndicate and Minor Food conclusion as follows.

S&P Syndicate's sustainability communication is focused on the "Planet" aspect of the Three Bottom Line theory. Their content consistently emphasizes health and well-being, equality and inclusion, reducing inequality, and sustainable community development. Key initiatives include comprehensive health insurance for employees, community health projects, and strict food safety measures. S&P also highlights gender equality through recognition of female leadership and participation in equality-promoting ceremonies. Their efforts to reduce inequality are demonstrated through vocational training for disadvantaged groups and support for local farmers. Additionally, S&P's community development projects, such as ecosystem restoration and food rescue, showcase their dedication to environmental conservation and social welfare. These themes collectively reflect S&P's commitment to social responsibility, environmental stewardship, and economic viability.

Minor Food's sustainability communication focuses more on the "People" and "Profit" aspects of the Three Bottom Line, with a strong emphasis on people development and innovative practices. Their initiatives include comprehensive health programs, educational partnerships, and training programs aimed at enhancing employee well-being and professional growth. Minor Food's content highlights their efforts to empower communities through various empowerment initiatives. They also adopt innovative technologies to improve operational efficiency and sustainability. Unlike S&P's local focus, Minor Food's communication strategy has a broader global reach, reflecting their impact on a wider scale. Their messaging demonstrates a professional image and a passion for sustainable achievement, aligning with global sustainability agendas.

Comparative Analysis

Both S&P Syndicate and Minor Food emphasize the importance of sustainability, but their approaches and focal points differ. S&P Syndicate places significant emphasis on community health, equality, and local community development, showcasing their commitment through detailed and locally focused initiatives. In contrast, Minor Food highlights global impact, innovative practices, and comprehensive health and empowerment programs, reflecting a broader and more diverse stakeholder engagement. These differences underscore each brand's unique strategy in

communicating their sustainability efforts, providing valuable insights for other businesses aiming to enhance their sustainability communication strategies.

Message Tone

Message Tone of S&P Syndicate and Minor Food conclusion is as follows.

The message tone analysis of S&P Syndicate reveals a strategic approach to sustainability communication that blends both cognitive and emotional engagement. By consistently using keywords like "Quality Value and Virtue" and "The Pursuit of Strength and Growth," S&P reinforces its commitment to sustainable practices across its website and social media channels, particularly through detailed content and visual storytelling. Employing both the central route of persuasion, with logical arguments and factual information, and the peripheral route, with engaging visuals and emotional narratives, S&P aims to connect with its audience on multiple levels. However, the absence of sustainability content on platforms like Instagram indicates a gap in their communication strategy, while a slight disconnect between some messages and the corporate brand suggests an opportunity for greater alignment. Overall, S&P effectively positions itself as a socially responsible corporation but could benefit from a more cohesive and integrated communication approach across all channels.

The message tone analysis of Minor Food demonstrates a well-coordinated and multi-faceted approach to communicating its sustainability efforts. Utilizing key phrases like "Minor is More," "People Build Brands," and "Great Place to Work," the company maintains a cohesive and recognizable narrative across all its platforms. Through the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM), Minor Food effectively combines both central and peripheral routes of persuasion: presenting detailed information and logical arguments about its sustainability practices to engage the audience cognitively while also using engaging visuals, emotional appeals, and personal stories to create a deeper emotional connection. The integration of various communication channels, such as prominently linking its website and social media platforms, ensures consistent messaging and easy navigation for users. This strategy fosters a sense of trust, credibility, and emotional engagement among stakeholders, enhancing their connection to the company's mission and values. By transparently showcasing its achievements and fostering pride and passion in these efforts, Minor Food not only strengthens its internal culture and stakeholder loyalty but also solidifies its reputation as a leader in corporate social responsibility, extending its influence in promoting sustainable practices throughout the community.

The comparative analysis of message tones between S&P Syndicate and Minor Food reveals distinct strategies in communicating their sustainability efforts through Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC), the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM), and narrative techniques. Both brands prioritize consistency in their sustainability messages but differ in their thematic focus; S&P Syndicate centers on "Quality, Value, and Virtue," emphasizing environmental sustainability, while Minor Food highlights "Minor is More" and "People Build Brands," focusing on human development. Minor Food employs a broader range of multimedia content across multiple social media platforms, ensuring a more integrated and seamless user experience, whereas S&P Syndicate primarily uses Facebook and demonstrates strong channel integration but with a narrower scope.

In applying the ELM, both companies effectively utilize central and peripheral routes to convey their sustainability messages, but with differing emphases. S&P Syndicate leans towards providing detailed information and logical arguments, fostering a cognitive engagement with their audience while also using visuals and emotional appeals to capture attention. Minor Food, however, balances this by combining comprehensive information with more extensive use of engaging visuals and emotional narratives, creating a compelling and relatable message. From a narrative perspective, S&P Syndicate emphasizes community involvement and charitable efforts but shows some disconnection between their messaging and brand identity. In contrast, Minor Food's strategy is more cohesive and aligned, consistently reinforcing its brand identity through professional imagery and storytelling that connects with a wider range of stakeholders. Overall, both brands demonstrate effective use of communication strategies, with S&P Syndicate focusing on environmental aspects and Minor Food balancing human development with broader engagement tactics.

Limitations and Recommendations for Future Studies

1. Future research could expand by comparing global brand communication strategies across different industries or sectors.
2. There is an opportunity for in-depth exploration of sustainability-related topics within the hospitality and service industries, particularly in gastronomy-related fields such as coffee shops and hotels.
3. Researchers may consider examining topics related to capturing value in a hyperconnected world through sustainable branding in the gastronomy industry. This could include areas such as eco-labeling on digital platforms or sustainable brand activism in food delivery services.
4. Further studies could explore new paradigms in customer-brand relationships concerning sustainability, such as sustainable leisure, luxury consumption, and the consumer journey.

Practical Implications for Restaurants' Sustainability Communication

Recommendations for Sustainable Communication Strategies: Local and Global Restaurants.

For Local Restaurants

1. Apply a Brand Portfolio Strategy: Utilize a brand portfolio approach that integrates both corporate and product brands to ensure consistent and clear sustainability messaging, enhancing overall communication effectiveness.
2. Use the Brand Archetype Model: Strategize content themes by employing the brand archetype model to identify a brand persona that aligns with the restaurant's unique identity and values.
3. Enhance Linkage Between Brand Purpose and Sustainability: Implement brand strategies that clearly link the brand's purpose to its sustainability messages, creating a coherent and compelling narrative.

For Global Restaurants

1. Integrate Local Culture in Communication: Incorporate local cultural elements into sustainability communication to balance global messages with local perceptions, thereby increasing awareness and engagement with local audiences.

2. Broaden Stakeholder Targeting: Expand and diversify the target audience of stakeholders to enhance the longevity and impact of sustainability initiatives.
3. Strengthen Customer Perception of Value: Apply brand strategies that reinforce customer value perception of sustainability messages, effectively communicating the brand's commitment to sustainable practices.

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Conflict of Interests

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